

The cage (see figure) consists of a wooden frame 45 cm wide × 52 cm high covered with nylon screen. The cage bottom is wood. Common air conditioner foam rubber filter is stapled on intercage wood surfaces.

The preferred oviposition substrate of wax paper strips (15.24 cm wide × 60.96 cm long) are held in place vertically by slipping the paper through slots in wooden slats at the top and bottom of the cage and securing with tape. Slots are partitioned 12.5 cm apart.

C. suppressalis and *C. polychrysus* pupae in petri dishes were placed in the cage. Female adults that emerged within the cage were observed to oviposit only on the wax paper. *T. incertulas* moths collected around light sources laid 80% of their egg masses on the wax paper.

An improved oviposition cage for rice stem borers, developed at IRRI.

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Varietal reaction to rice gall midge

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Field resistance to rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed during 1981 kharif on prerelease cultivars and recommended varieties at Aduthurai. Test varieties were grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times. Recommended agro-nomic practices were followed except no insect control was used.

Gall midge damage was assessed 60 days after planting as the number of silver shoots among total tillers in 10 hills selected at random from each plot. Rating was by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Of the entries tested only IET3231 had no damage. Five entries recorded less than 5% damage (see table).

Gall midge damage at Tamil Nadu, India, 1981 kharif.

Variety	Parentage	Duration (days)	Damage (%)	Rating
IET3231	IR8/Siam 29	135	0.0	0
IET6010	IR8/W1263	127	0.5	1
IET6290	Leaung/IR8	135	0.8	1
IET6282	Leaung/IR8	130	4.4	3
IET6074	Vijaya/Ptb 21	130	2.3	3
IET5975	OR 10-135/W1263	130	5.0	3
IR20	IR262/TKM6	135	9.1	5
Jaya	TN1/T141	125	9.8	5
Jagannath	Mutant of T141	150	18.0	7
Pankaj (susceptible check)	Peta/Tongai Rotam	150	34.7	7
CD				11.66

Gall midge collections needed

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Discrepancies in reports on host ranges and other biological information on *Orseolia oryzae* in Asia and Africa indi-

cate a need for basic taxonomic research. Such research must be based on adequate collections of reared series from cultivated rice and from suspected wild grass hosts.

The materials needed include adult males and females with associated larvae, pupae, and pupal cases; data on host plant species and cultivars; type of